

POWER SYSTEM REAL TIME MONITORING AND CONTROL

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ABSTRACT:

Power system reliability has been thrust into the limelight by recent blackouts around the world. The -social and economic costs of these failures can add up to billions of -dollars every year. As the digital age prevails, more efficient manufacturing processes, based on computers and power electronics, have come to -dominate industry. As the portion of electricity in the total energy consumption continues to grow, the value of power system reliability increases. This article discusses a vision for state-of-the-art solutions to improve power system reliability through -improved monitoring and control.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The likelihood of blackouts has been increasing because of various physical and economic factors. These include (1) the demand for larger power transfers over longer -distances, (2) insufficient investment in the transmission system, exacerbated by continued load growth, (3) huge swings in power flow patterns from one day to the next that render classic off-line planning studies ineffective, and (4) the consolidation of operating entities. These factors result in larger operational footprints and greater -demands on the operator to deal with smaller error margins and shorter -decision times. These circumstances have created a less reliable operating environment by pushing power -systems close to their physical limits. Such an environment requires more intensive on-line analyses to better-coordinate controls across the entire grid. Wide-area monitoring and control tools, eg, Phasor Measurement Units (PMU) and Flexible AC Transmission System (FACTS) devices, and distributed generation and storage devices are the primary technologies used to address such problems. The role of FACTS devices in measures to counter blackouts is -described in [1].